

**ЕНДОСКОПІЧНІ ТРАНСПАПІЛЯРНІ ВТРУЧАННЯ У ЛІКУВАННІ
ЖОВЧНОКАМ'ЯНОЇ ХВОРОБИ, УСКЛАДНЕНОЇ НЕПРОХІДНІСТЮ
ТЕРМІНАЛЬНОГО ВІДДІЛУ ХОЛЕДОХА**

**ENDOSCOPIC TRANSPAPILLARY INTERVENTIONS IN THE
TREATMENT OF GALLSTONE DISEASE COMPLICATED BY
OBSTRUCTION OF THE TERMINAL CHOLEDOCHUS**

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Gallstone disease is a disease of the liver and bile ducts caused by the formation of stones in the gallbladder and bile ducts. According to the WHO, the number of people suffering from gallstone disease is 10-15% of the total population of Europe. In addition, the incidence rate has tripled in the last 30 years, in part due to improved diagnosis. Surgical activity against cholelithiasis, which was observed during the second half of the twentieth century, led to the predominance of operations on the biliary tract over the other abdominal operations.

The aim of the work is to optimize the existing and develop new methods of endoscopic transpapillary interventions in gallstone disease complicated by obstruction of the terminal choledochus, to reduce the incidence of postoperative complications and mortality.

Materials and methods. From 2017 to 2021, 288 patients with complicated gallstones were treated at the Department of General Surgery and Postgraduate Surgical Education of Zaporizhia State Medical University. Women accounted for 211 (73.26%), men 77 (26.74%) in accordance. The age gradation of the examined patients was based on the classification adopted at the WHO International Symposium on Gerontology. There were 148 (82.7%) aged 60 to 74 years, and 31 (17.3%) patients aged 75 to 90 years.

The instrumental examination included an ultrasound examination of the abdominal cavity, endoscopic esophagogastroduodenoscopy, magnetic resonance cholangiopancreatography, and computed tomography of the abdominal cavity.

Research results and its discussion. The most common cause of obstruction of the terminal choledochus of the gallstone disease was stenosis of the major duodenal papilla in combination with choledocholithiasis, which was found in 66 (37.1%) patients. Other causes were the major duodenal papilla stenosis in 52 (28.9%), the major duodenal papilla wedge in 27 (14.9%), choledocholithiasis in 21 (11.8%), and

chronic cephalic pancreatitis in 13 (7.3%). 164 (91.4%) patients had mechanical jaundice syndrome, 60 (33.1%) had acute cholangitis, and 14 (8.1%) had acute biliary pancreatitis. Cholecystectomy was previously performed in 28 (15.8%) patients. All patients underwent surgery.

Endoscopic methods of correction of obstruction of the terminal choledochus included endoscopic papillosphincterotomy, endoscopic choledocholithotomy, and choledocholithoextraction, less often endoscopic suprapapillary choledochoduodenostomy, as well as one of the options for drainage of the extrahepatic bile ducts.

After the normalization of clinical and laboratory indications, another stage was laparoscopic cholecystectomy. With the impossibility of endoscopic correction of obstruction of the terminal choledochus, the disease was treated with laparotomy and choledocholithotomy and drainage of the extrahepatic bile ducts.

Thus, the use of existing and proposed new methods of endoscopic interventions in gallstone disease complicated by obstruction of the terminal choledochus has significantly reduced the incidence of postoperative complications and postoperative mortality.

Conclusions. Endoscopic transpapillary methods of surgical treatment of gallstone disease complicated by obstruction of the terminal choledochus are highly effective and minimize the incidence of postoperative complications and mortality.